

330 MW Thermal Power Plant Development in Kumasi, Ghana A Financial Viability and Sensitivity Analysis Using FINPLAN

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Executive Summary

Ghana has made significant progress in electricity access, reaching approximately 89.5% nationwide. However, rising electricity demand, system reliability challenges, and reserve margins below international best practice continue to pressure the power system. This study evaluates the financial viability of a proposed 330 MW thermal power plant in Kumasi using the Model for Financial Analysis of Electric Sector Expansion Plans (FINPLAN), with particular focus on tariff adequacy and exchange rate risk. The analysis finds that a minimum electricity tariff of approximately GHS1.01/kWh is required to ensure both project viability and bankability, maintaining a debt service coverage ratio (DSCR) of at least 1.3 and positive net present value (NPV). Sensitivity analysis further shows that the project remains bankable up to about 15% annual exchange rate depreciation, beyond which debt-servicing capacity deteriorates. The results highlight the importance of cost-reflective tariffs and exchange-rate risk management to attract generation investment and sustain reliable electricity supply. Policy recommendations include adopting realistic tariff setting and introducing mechanisms to mitigate foreign exchange risk

1. Introduction

Ghana's electricity sector has achieved substantial gains in access over recent decades, supported by investments in generation, transmission, and distribution infrastructure (World Bank, 2023). Despite this progress, the power system continues to face challenges related to reliability, rising demand, and reserve margin adequacy. The Energy Commission of Ghana has noted that system reserve margins remain below the international benchmark of approximately 18%, increasing vulnerability during periods of peak demand. (Energy Commission, 2023)

Recent policy efforts, including the extension of gas transmission infrastructure into the Middle Belt and plans for additional generation capacity, are intended to strengthen system reliability and reduce transmission constraints. In this context, a careful financial appraisal of new power projects is essential to ensure sustainability for both investors and consumers.

The purpose of this study is to assess the financial viability of a proposed 330 MW thermal power plant in Kumasi using the Model for Financial Analysis of Electric Sector Expansion Plans (FINPLAN). Specifically, the study seeks to;

1. Identify the minimum electricity tariff that balances investor sustainability and consumer protection, and
2. Assess the impact of Exchange-Rate volatility on the project viability and bankability that poses a binding constraint on project viability.

2. Methodology

This study applies the FINPLAN financial modelling tool to evaluate the viability of a 330 MW combined-cycle plant. FINPLAN is a project-level financial analysis model commonly used to assess infrastructure investments by estimating key financial indicators such as internal rate of return (IRR), net present value (NPV), and debt service coverage ratio (DSCR). The model simulates project cash flows over a 30-year operating life of the plant, with construction in 2025 and 2026 and commercial operations commencing in 2027. The financial viability is assessed by employing the use of NPV while DSCR is used as the primary bankability metric. NPV measures profitability, while DSCR measures the project's ability to service debt. DSCR is defined as the ratio of cash available for debt service to total debt obligations. Lenders typically require a minimum DSCR of 1.3 for power projects (Yescombe, 2014). Ghana's regulatory benchmark for DSCR is also 1.3 and is employed in this analysis

2.1 Data Sources and Assumptions

Key technical and financial assumptions are based on typical parameters for thermal power plants in Ghana. Table 1.0 captures the technical, economic and financial assumptions as well as data sources for the project.

Table 1: Summary of Parameters and Assumptions Underpinning 330MW Thermal Power Plant -Kumasi Ghana

No.	Parameter	Measure	Value
1	Capacity	MW	330
2	Plant Availability	%	92
3	Annual Energy	GWh	2,660
4	Project Lifespan	Years	30
5	Construction Years	Years	2
6	Year of First Operation	Year	2027
7	Project Cost	MUSD	426.32
8	Debt Component	MUSD	300.00
9	Equity Component	MGHS	1,326.36
10	Discount Rate	%	9.60
11	Operation and Maintenance Costs	MUSD	26.52
12	Fuel Cost	MUSD	132.00
13	Exchange Rate	GHS/USD	10.50
14	Inflation	%	
14a	Foreign Inflation	%	2
14b	Local Inflation	%	5
15	Taxes	%	
15a	VAT (80 percent on investment)	%	20
15b	Income Tax	%	25

2.2 Sensitivity Analysis

Sensitivity analysis is used in testing how changes in key regulatory and macroeconomic variables affect the financial viability and bankability of the project. The financial viability and bankability are assessed using NPV and the DSCR, respectively, by varying the variables electricity tariffs and exchange rates. The Sensitivity Analysis are summarized in Table 2.0 below

Table 2: Summary of Sensitivity Analysis Framework

No.	Sensitivity Test	Base Case	Range Tested	Indicators Measured
1	Electricity Tariff Sensitivity	GHS 1.1521/kWh	0% to -25% [5% steps]	NPV, DSCR
2	Exchange Rate Sensitivity	GHS10.5/USD	0% to 30% [5% steps]	NPV, DSCR

3. Results

This section presents the results of the financial modelling and sensitivity analysis carried out using the FINPLAN tool. The analysis focuses on how changes in electricity tariffs and exchange rate depreciation affect the profitability and bankability of the proposed 330 MW thermal power plant. Project performance is assessed using Net Present Value (NPV) and the Debt Service Coverage Ratio (DSCR), with particular emphasis on DSCR as the key indicator of bankability.

3.1 Tariff Sensitivity Results

The tariff sensitivity analysis shows that electricity tariff levels play a decisive role in determining both the financial viability and bankability of the project. Under the base-case tariff of 1.1521 GHS/kWh, the project performs strongly, achieving a DSCR of 1.70 and a positive NPV of approximately GHS 10,559 million. This indicates a comfortable margin for servicing debt and generating returns.

As tariffs are reduced, the project performance deteriorates steadily. Both NPV and DSCR decline, reflecting reduced revenue available to cover operating costs and debt obligations. The analysis identifies a critical threshold at a tariff of approximately GHS1.0138 /kWh, where DSCR falls to 1.3. Figure 3.1 illustrates this threshold clearly by showing the intersection between the DSCR and tariff lines. At this level, the project remains profitable but any further tariff reduction pushes DSCR below the bankability threshold. For example, at a tariff of 0.9793 GHS/kWh, DSCR declines to 1.20, indicating that while the project may still generate positive cash flows, it would likely struggle to meet lender requirements. Figure 3.2 further highlights how declining tariffs simultaneously weaken profitability and debt-servicing capacity.

Figure 1: Tariff Sensitivity Decision Chart

Figure 2 Tariff Sensitivity, Profitability and Bankability

3.2 Exchange Rate Sensitivity Results

The exchange rate sensitivity analysis highlights the exposure of the project to macroeconomic risk, particularly currency depreciation. As the exchange rate depreciates,

DSCR declines due to the USD-denominated nature of debt and fuel costs, while project revenues remain in Ghana cedis.

The results as depicted in Figure 3.3 shows that the project remains bankable up to approximately 15% annual exchange rate depreciation, at which point DSCR reaches 1.3. Beyond this level, debt-servicing capacity deteriorates rapidly even though the project remains profitable as per the NPV values presented in Figure 3.4. At 20% depreciation, DSCR falls to 1.10, signalling that the project would face difficulty meeting debt obligations despite remaining operational.

Figure 3 Exchange Rate Sensitivity Decision Chart

Figure 4 Exchange Rate Sensitivity, Profitability and Bankability

3.3 Key Findings

Overall, the results show that tariff levels are the main controllable lever for ensuring project bankability, while exchange rate depreciation represents a binding external risk. Maintaining tariffs above the identified minimum of GHS 1.0138/kWh and managing foreign exchange rate depreciation below 15% exposure are therefore critical to sustaining investment and financing for power generation projects.

4. Discussion

The findings from this study offer important insights into the financial conditions required to support sustainable power sector investments in Ghana. The tariff sensitivity analysis clearly shows that electricity pricing plays a central role in determining both project viability and bankability. While tariffs set below GHS1.0138 /kWh may appear attractive from a short-term affordability perspective, the results demonstrate that such pricing undermines the ability of power projects to meet lender requirements. In particular, tariffs below the identified minimum bankable level reduce DSCR to levels that increase financing risk, potentially discouraging private investment and weakening long-term system reliability.

The exchange rate sensitivity analysis further highlights the importance of macroeconomic stability in the performance of thermal power projects. Given Ghana's continued major reliance on foreign-currency financing, exchange rate depreciation directly increases operating costs and debt service obligations. The finding that project bankability is breached beyond approximately 15% annual depreciation indicates that foreign exchange risk is not a marginal consideration, but a binding constraint that can materially affect investment outcomes. Even where profitability remains positive, declining DSCR signals heightened difficulty in meeting debt obligations, which may limit access to financing.

Taken together, these results suggest that regulators face a delicate balancing task. On one hand, there is a need to protect consumers from excessive tariff increases; on the other, electricity prices must remain sufficient to sustain investment, attract financing, and support reliable system operation. The analysis indicates that maintaining cost-reflective tariffs, alongside measures to manage exchange rate exposure, is critical to achieving this balance.

Foreign exchange risk in power projects can be managed through a combination of tariff indexation, contractual risk-sharing, and targeted guarantees. Tariff indexation allows electricity prices to adjust gradually in line with changes in key cost drivers such as the exchange rate, helping projects recover rising foreign-currency costs without sudden tariff shocks to consumers. Risk-sharing provisions in contracts can further distribute exchange-rate exposure between utilities and investors, while targeted guarantees may be used

selectively to cushion extreme currency movements. In Ghana, exchange-rate adjustments are already applied through quarterly tariff reviews, and the findings of this study support the continued use—and gradual strengthening—of this approach to preserve project bankability while maintaining consumer protection.

This study is subject to several limitations. The analysis assumes fixed fuel prices and broader system-level dynamics such as dispatch interactions with other plants and network constraints which are not explicitly captured. These limitations highlight opportunities for further analysis and refinement of the model. As part of future work emanating from this study, other parameters including Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and dividend payouts equally important indicators which could be employed for future work on the model. Additionally, the use of the FINPLAN model to train regulators and planners for better power-sector decisions is another future work worth considering.

7. Conclusion

This study evaluated the financial viability and bankability of a proposed 330 MW thermal power plant in Kumasi using the FINPLAN model, with particular focus on electricity tariff adequacy and exchange rate risk. The results show that a minimum electricity tariff of approximately GHS1.01 /kWh is required to ensure both project profitability and lender acceptability, maintaining DSCR at or above 1.3, the commonly accepted thresholds. The analysis also indicates that the project can tolerate exchange rate depreciation of up to about 15% per year, beyond which debt-servicing capacity deteriorates and bankability is compromised.

The key conclusion is that financially sustainable power sector investments depend on both realistic tariff setting and effective management of macroeconomic risks. Tariffs that fall below cost-reflective levels may undermine investment incentives and system reliability, while unmanaged foreign exchange exposure can erode bankability even for otherwise profitable projects. Policymakers and regulators should therefore prioritise cost-reflective tariff frameworks and explore appropriate mechanisms to mitigate exchange rate risk.

Future work should extend the analysis to include tariff indexation and hedging options, improve the granularity of fuel price and exchange rate data. Additionally, the FINPLAN model should be more broadly used as a capacity-building tool for power sector planning and investment appraisal in Ghana.

8.References

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